

THE CONTENT OF MOTIVATING EMPLOYEES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of the content of employee motivation, innovative management, and different approaches to it in higher education. An analysis of the views of foreign and domestic scientists is presented. A description of the hierarchy of needs of the theories of A. Maslow and K. Alderfer is presented. In McClelland's theory, he distinguished three types of externalities similar to M. Weber's theory: power, wealth, prestige. The theories put forward by Maslow, McClelland, Herzberg, Victor Vroom, Porter and Lawler are covered in detail, as well as widely used theories of motivation in the field of management. The theory of D. Adams "Theory of Justice" was analyzed. According to him, if people evaluate the fairness of the results of their work in relation to others, then any injustice becomes a motivating state of the human mind.*

Keywords: *higher education, employees, motive, motivation, management, desire, Frederic Herzberg's "hygiene factors", A. Maslow's pyramid of needs, D. McGregory "Human Relations" school, "X" and "Y" theory, Dj. Adams theory of justice.*

Introduction. Employee motivation is one of the topics that occupies a large place in management psychology. Unfortunately, the word motivation is overused in everyday communication today. In this regard, we will talk about the psychological meaning of the word motivation and the possibility of its use in management practice. Motivation comes from the word motive and means a reason for an action. As the basis of activity, one or another need first appears in a person, after which an action is taken to satisfy the need. It is the internal force that motivates this action, and a set of motives that come into play during the satisfaction of the motive and need is called motivation. Motivation in the field of management means encouraging an employee or work team to work towards the goals of the organization. Mainly since the second half of the 20th century, theories, rules, principles, methods and technologies of motivation in various fields have been studied on a large scale by a number of disciplines, and today this knowledge is being further improved. It is observed that researches in this field are more advanced than modern ones in developed and democratic countries.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Despite the widespread practice of using the mechanism of motivating employees, there is a big difference in the definitions of the concept of "motivation". These differences are largely determined by the author's affiliation to a field of science (economics, management, psychology, sociology, or other).

The study of motivation issues in management, administrative law and political science, personnel management has significantly expanded. In developed countries, it has become a tradition to call the management and personnel of the state, society and other sectors at various levels "subjects of motivation", and all other personnel in the field of production "objects of motivation". It is known that subjects of motivation have different effects on objects. Motivation means an external influence on a person's work behavior to achieve the goals of the individual,

group and society. When choosing the forms and methods of motivation, first of all, it is necessary to take into account the factors that motivate a person to this or that action. Motivation (lat. moveo - "movement") is a psychophysical process that drives a person to certain activities and controls his behavior. The result of the activity directly depends on the process of motivating personnel. Views on the culture of managing people are widely described in the first religious-philosophical literature in "Avesta", "Torah", "Bible", "Vedas", especially the great spiritual heritage of the peoples of the East is expressed in detail in "Avesta". [1]. In the Avesta, it is mentioned that the main duties of people are knowledge and wisdom, intelligence, benevolence and well-being, peace and stability, oppression, enmity, and the just resolution of conflicts. to do is to lose one's own peace for the sake of others", he says. In general, our ancestors like Farobi, Beruni, Ibn Sina and Amir Timur saw development in the harmony of goals and interests. In this regard, the views of Farobi are particularly noteworthy [2].

The first modern and classical concepts of scientific motivation appeared at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. Later, the theories put forward by Maslow, McClelland, Herzberg, Victor Vroom, Porter and Lawler have become widely used theories of motivation in management. The theories of A. Maslow and K. Alderfer are known as the theory of the hierarchy of needs[3,4]. In McClelland's theory, he distinguished three types of externalities similar to M. Weber's theory: power, wealth, prestige. The theory of D. Adams is called "Theory of Justice". He claims that if people evaluate the fairness of their labor results in relation to others, then any injustice becomes a motivating state of human consciousness [7].

Research methodology. In the methodology of this article, the methods of analysis and synthesis, scientific abstraction, deduction, classification, generalization, comparative, theoretical interpretation were used. In addition, the scientific basis of the article consists of international standards and regulatory documents, information obtained from the research of local and foreign scientists in scientific publications.

Analysis and results. By the 50s of the 20th century, the school of human relations in management was improved based on the views of the behavioral school or the school of behavioral sciences. According to its characteristics, the ideas of this school arose as a result of applying the achievements of psychology and sociology, i.e., the sciences related to human behavior, in management. The main idea of this direction is not only to develop methods of establishing human relations in the organization, but also to increase the labor efficiency of individual workers and the entire organization based on behavioral sciences. Its founders are R. Likert, D. McGregor, K. Alferder, F. Hertzberg and others. It was developed in 1964 by the American psychologist W. Vroom. Its essence is that motivation is not only about satisfying a need, but also about a chosen desire to achieve a goal. In the theory of expectations, the interaction of 3 important factors plays a key role. The more the expectation leads to satisfaction, the stronger the motivation. This means that in addition to the concept of need, the leader must create situations in which complex, difficult work is well paid and mentally stimulated. The essence of the theory of expectations requires this [4].

V. Vroom's theory of "Expectation" represents the definition of working motivation based on the interdependence of the individual's actions, work efficiency and results [8]. Motivation is the management of consequences as a result of behavior. This approach is based on D. F. Skinner's theory [9]. He classified the employee's behavior as follows: behavior that occurs as a result of incentives and behavior that occurs as a result of waiting for incentives. E. L. Thorndike's "Effect

Theory" is the basis of the management of consequences in motivation theory. "Effectiveness theory" is simply expressed but has great power, that is, it makes the behavior that leads to a good outcome more likely to be repeated, while the behavior that leads to an undesirable outcome is less likely to be repeated[10]. Inappropriate behavior leads to negative incentives, i.e. punishment. The employee does not want negative incentives to be applied to him. It should be mentioned that the supporters of the theory of "scientific motivation" interpreted it as a sphere of society with equal rights and equal value.

D. McGregor is one of the prominent representatives of the "Human Relations" school. He created the theory of "X" and "Y", taking into account two models of human behavior, the possibility of an employee having two different attitudes to his work. According to the "X" theory, the employee is lazy by nature, so he tries to evade the assigned work, he lacks ambition, sense of responsibility, understanding. In this case, it is necessary to constantly threaten the employee with coercion, control, punishment and fines.

Theory "Y" is the opposite of the first one: workers are active by nature, they are characterized by initiative and perseverance, taking responsibility. In such a case, the manager's task is to create the conditions under which people can achieve their goals and interests in an optimal way. The policy and perspective of the company should be organized based on the behavior of the employees. According to this theory, it is enough to encourage the incoming worker and create a comfortable environment for him [4].

According to the theory of fairness, people compare the level of incentive they have achieved with the level of incentive achieved by other people employed in the same system. According to Dj.Adams, the cost includes not only the employee's labor spent on this work, but also his seniority, skill level, age, social status, etc.

If all evaluations and comparisons do not result in unfairness, then motivational factors will have a positive effect on the employee. If everyone is treated equally, then the employee will be empowered and work hard, and vice versa, that is, if the employee feels that there is injustice, if there is inequality in incentives, then conflicts will arise in the enterprise. As long as people are not rewarded according to their work, ability, knowledge and intelligence, they will not try to increase productivity and efficiency. The atmosphere of harmony in the enterprise is not settled. Based on these factors, a successful leader leads others with his confidence. Motivation is not just about giving out rewards. Fair punishment of employees who failed to perform their duties or violated labor discipline encourages them to improve their performance.

According to A. Maslow's theory about the pyramid of needs, the actual need in a person is reflected in the appropriate motive and he performs activities accordingly. According to this doctrine, all human needs and corresponding motives can be classified into seven main groups[3]:

1. Physiological needs include the need to ensure the biological integrity of the human body: food, rest, housing, etc. One of the main conditions for meeting these listed needs is having a sufficient amount of money. Thus, material wealth, salary, social opportunities are a way to satisfy basic physiological needs.

2. The need for security - preservation of life, health, trust in the future, trust in pension provision, etc.

3. The need for affection. Acceptance of a person in his community, his recognition, attention and love of others towards him.

4. The need for respect and prestige. Recognition of one's identity and need for the organization, to feel respect for oneself in the surrounding people, to have a high position.

5. The need for self-improvement. Strive to further demonstrate one's abilities, develop them, engage in creative activities, and realize the meaning of one's life.

6. Aesthetic needs. A person strives for aesthetic feelings and emotions during his life and work. Aesthetic needs serve to beautify a person's life and perfect the results of his work during his work. This gives meaning to human life.

7. The need to develop one's personality always motivates a person to work on himself, increase his knowledge, and demonstrate his abilities, and a person always strives for this.

According to A. Maslow, the motives of the higher level show their activity only after the needs of the first and second levels are sufficiently satisfied. The leader will have the opportunity to apply the appropriate type of attitude to the employee only if he knows the specific needs of the subordinate. So, the unsatisfied need is the impetus for the activity, and the actual need is the main resource that controls the activity. A. Maslow's doctrine of the hierarchy of motives is very useful for understanding the behavior of the organization's employees and for creating the necessary conditions for managing them in a targeted direction. Satisfying the need for recognition at the organization level can be done by involving the employee in the life of the organization, in making management decisions. It is this need that motivates a person to become a skilled master of his profession, it is the leading factor to be recognized by others as a mature specialist.

The starting point of any motivation is a need that needs to be satisfied. Then the goal related to meeting this need is determined. A defined goal and a perceived need begin to search for an object to satisfy this need, and a person realizes this goal. It is possible to control the behavior of others by identifying a specific need and taking measures to satisfy it.

Based on this idea, the main idea of motivating employees can be stated as follows. Harmonization of the interests that represent the organization's purpose with the needs of the employee is the main condition for effective management of employees. Usually, when an employee comes to an organization, there is always an internal force that motivates him to work, that is, a need that needs to be satisfied. The leader can ensure the unity of the goals of the employee and the organization by correctly identifying this need and harmonizing it with the interests of the organization. This is one of the main strengths of the employee in realizing the organization's goals.

Organizational management is a concept that expresses itself as a whole system, as well as a specific system of rules related to the conduct of people's activities in it. In the practice of management of the organization, the use of this or that personnel is based on the need to put them in their place, to use specific methods of increasing efficiency. Based on this, the concept of innovative management is defined:

Innovation management is the end result of creative activity embodied in the form of a new or improved product or technology that can be used in practice and is able to meet specific needs. In other words, innovation is the result of the implementation of new ideas and knowledge for the purpose of practical use to satisfy certain needs of consumers (A.V. Surin, O.P. Molchanova). Innovation management is the final result of the creation and development [3] of fundamentally new or modified tools (innovations) that satisfy competitive social needs and provide a number of results (economic, scientific-technical, social, technological) (A.A. Shemetev).

Innovation management is a method (technology) of a new or improved product (goods, work, service), its production or application, innovation or organization of production and (or) improvement of the economy and (or) product sales, which brings economic benefits. creating conditions for benefits or improving consumer characteristics of products (goods, works, services) (A.S. Kulagin)

Innovative management is the introduction and use of new types of goods, new methods and methods of production, new sources of raw materials, new markets and changes in production factors based on entrepreneurial spirit (new combinations); new forms of production organization (reorganization for the purpose of monopolization) (T. Schumpeter).

Innovation management is a special tool of entrepreneurs who use change as an opportunity to implement a new type of business or service. Innovation is the development and implementation of something new that did not exist before, with the help of which old, familiar elements give new contours to the economy of this business (Peter F. Drucker)

Accordingly, management motivation tasks are formed as follows:

- that all work carried out with personnel is subordinated to the requirements of the necessary level of professional skills, to ensure the interests and activities of employees at a continuous and high-quality level;
- rational use of the personnel potential under the care of associations, organizations and enterprises;
- formation and support of a hard-working, mutually friendly production team, development of principles of labor process organization processes;
- development of internal production democracy; - development of criteria and methods of placement, training and selection of personnel with high professional skills; retraining and upgrading the skills of the main part of working employees;
- development of the theory of personnel management and the principles of determining the social and economic effectiveness of the doctrines included in this field.

At present, a number of theories have been developed regarding the retention of personnel, their motivation and improvement of their labor efficiency, the management, orientation, etc. of these labors, including F.U. Taylor's "scientific management", A. Maslow and Alderfer's "hierarchical needs of the individual", F. Herzberg's "vertical and horizontal expansion of incentives", Adams' "equality in work and pay", W. Vroom's "valence, instrumentality, results or recognition and trust", McClelland's "power, success, interest needs", R. Likert's "human relations", B. Skinner's "operational connection", L. Porter and E. Lawler's "justice" theories reflecting the process of personnel management in the market economy are especially widely used in practice. In these theories, importance is mainly focused on improving labor efficiency in the activities of workers in general

The general employee motivation system is based on several basic principles:

Transparency. This principle helps to choose transparent methods of motivation and incentives that are clear for each employee. When motivating, it is necessary to take into account seniority, position, volume of work, contribution to the success of the enterprise, creative approach and other factors.

Systematic. At the same time, it does not make sense to reward employees with large sums of money or other intangible incentives. In order to encourage employees to constantly achieve new goals, motivation is carried out step by step.

Effectiveness. Any form of motivation is supposed to be effective, based on specific achievements of the employee, and be fair.

Timeliness. Shows the importance of the time factor in motivating employees. Employee achievements should be recorded in some way immediately. Delaying the incentive period is not recommended. The employee should always feel that his work is needed.

Integrity. This principle implies appropriate use of various types of motivation, material and non-material rewards.

The main stages of introducing the employee motivation system in the organization are as follows: creation of employee incentive systems; organization of a working group; setting specific goals and objectives of employee motivation; developing an employee incentive plan; development of reward programs for achieving set goals; preparation of documents; implementation of motivation activities and introduction of necessary changes; consists of analyzing the activity of the employee motivation system.

Types of employee motivation. In practice, there are two main types of employee motivation: tangible and intangible. Intangible motivation of employees, in turn, is divided into two types: social and psychological motivation of employees.

So, material motivation of employees. As a rule, material motivation of employees is used a lot in organizations. Components of financial motivation of employees: specific performance indicators of the employee; that the optimal proportions of the permanent and bonus parts of the salary are established; orientation of the employee's work quality and time to the motivation system. Types of material motivation of employees. Material motivation of employees is their direct encouragement through monetary means. Incentive employees through indirect material (souvenir (non-monetary)).

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